

Applications of wavelets in Power Quality Disturbances

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Abstract

Poor power quality may cause many problems for affected loads such as malfunctions, instabilities and short lifetime. The dependence of modern life upon the continuous supply of electrical energy makes power quality topic of utmost importance in the power systems area. The increased requirements on supervision control and performance in modern power systems makes power quality and to take proper mitigating actions the sources and causes of such disturbances should be known. To determine the causes and sources of disturbances one must detect and localize those disturbances and classify the types of the disturbances. New tools are required to extract all relevant information from the recordings in an automatic way. Detection, localization and quantification of voltage and current disturbances are important tasks in monitoring and protection of distribution systems. The concept of Discrete Wavelet Transform for feature extraction of power quality disturbance signals has been incorporated as a powerful tool for detecting and classifying power quality problems. This paper presents the ability of multiresolution signal decomposition technique, by plotting variations, standard deviations of the decomposed signal at different resolution levels, to classify and quantify the power quality disturbance. It has been also shown that the curve obtained by plotting the entropy of the decomposed signal at different levels provides clear information for the detection and quantification of the power quality disturbances.

Keywords: Power quality, voltage events, wavelet transform, entropy.

1. Introduction

A voltage event is an abnormal and temporary variation of the magnitude of voltage supply. Voltage dips, short interruption and voltage swells are the most important events in voltage consumers due to sensitivity of equipment to the voltage variations. It introduced the use of wavelet transform and multi resolution signal decomposition as a powerful analysis tool that can be used to monitor and measure the system response to distorted signals. It presented unique features that characterize power quality events and methodologies to extract them from recorded voltage and combiner and a fuzzy expert system for the classification of transient disturbances waveforms in a power system had been of a continuous wavelet transform to detect and analyze voltage sags and transients.

They developed an efficient and simple algorithm for power quality analysis. It presented an expert system that is able to classify different types of power system events and offer useful information in terms of power quality. The expert system uses the voltage waveforms and distinguishes the different types of voltage dips as well as interruptions. Gaing implemented and tested a prototype wavelet based neural network classifier for recognizing power quality disturbances. The discrete wavelet transform technique quality disturbances. The discrete wavelet transform technique has been integrated with the probabilistic neural network model to construct the classifier. The need to analyze power quality signals to extract their distinctive features made Gargoom et al to use Hilbert transform and Clarke transform for the classification of power quality signals and they compared the performance of these techniques with wavelet transform. Used DWTs to detect high impedance faults due to leaning trees. Wireless sensors have been considered for processing the DWTs. Mishra et al presented an S transform based probabilistic neural network classifier for the recognition of power quality disturbances. A new method has been proposed by Peres and Barros for the online real-time detection and classification of voltage events in power systems. They used wavelet analysis for the detection and estimation of time related parameters of an event and used extended Kalman filtering for the confirmation of the event.

The aim of this paper is to present the applications multiresolution analysis as a powerful tool for detecting, classifying and quantifying short duration power quality disturbances. The disturbances are sag, swell and interruption. The localization and duration of the disturbance has been detected using